

Original Research

TIS Company's Audio and Video System Product Strategy Research

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Abstract

With the continuous development of the audio and video industry, there is an increasing amount of information that needs to be processed, and competition in the professional audio and video system market is becoming increasingly fierce. In such a competitive environment, adopting the right product strategy is crucial for products to successfully enter and occupy the market. This paper takes TIS Company's audio and video system products as the research object. Firstly, it analyzes the macro and micro environments of TIS Company's audio and video market to understand the current development trends and mainstream directions of the professional audio and video market. Combining the SWOT analysis method, it analyzes TIS's internal strengths and weaknesses, market opportunities, and threats. It also analyzes the four types of TIS's product portfolio strategy to provide a reference for developing effective product strategies for TIS's products. Under this premise, based on TIS Company's existing resource situation, it analyzes its current product strategy and finds issues such as overly tight product combinations and unreasonable pricing of new products. Therefore, optimization suggestions for the product strategy are proposed, such as reducing product length, clarifying product brand positioning, increasing brand exposure, and introducing technology to strengthen product inventory management. These suggestions aim to improve TIS Company's brand awareness in the audio and video system market, make more potential enterprises aware of TIS Company, and promote mutual benefit and win-win cooperation between TIS Company, the entire audio and video system industry, and even the entire audio and video integrated circuit industry. This study aims to provide some guidance and reference for TIS's audio and video system product strategy.

Keywords: audio and video system; product strategy; product portfolio; product management

Introduction

(A) Research Background

Audio and video systems are multidisciplinary and application-oriented industries that focus on auditory and visual experiences. Professional audio and video systems are complex and require the optimal integration of various technologies, including optics, electroacoustics, artistic aesthetics, computer science, and communication technology. They typically utilize audio, video, and control systems, with the control system serving as the core. Depending on functional needs, lighting or illumination systems, internal communication systems, and stage mechanical systems may also be integrated.

Professional audio and video systems are high-tech industries with diverse applications, such as in conferences and exhibitions, cultural and sports venues, cultural tourism, entertainment venues, broadcasting and television centers, film and television production centers, commercial centers, judicial authorities, energy and power sectors, campuses, and hotels. Since the 21st century, with the rapid development of Internet technology, professional audio and video technology applications have also achieved unprecedented growth. For example, online distribution of digital audio and video, real-time remote collaboration, and remote video surveillance are widely used in various industries. Meanwhile, emerging technologies such as HD, 3D, 4K, and 8K are laying a solid foundation for the future development of professional audio and video technology.

As the audio and video industry continues to grow, the need to process information increases. In recent years, the scale of Thailand's professional audio and video industry has continuously expanded, with a market growth rate higher than the global average. Investments in smart education and smart healthcare in Thailand have driven the demand for professional audio and video systems, leading to deeper applications of these systems in offices, culture, sports, entertainment, and other fields.

In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted on product strategies in various industries, including manufacturing, retail, and service sectors. However, relatively few have focused on the professional audio and video systems sector, particularly in the context of Southeast Asia. According to Venkatesh (2016), product strategy must consider both internal capabilities and external market dynamics, especially pricing and competitive forces. This principle is critical in the audio-video market, where technological advancements rapidly reshape customer expectations. Existing research has emphasized the importance of product portfolio management and market positioning in maintaining competitiveness (Trout & Ries, 2002). In the context of professional AV systems, technological integration—such as with 4K/8K displays, IoT, and AI-based video processing—has become a key differentiator for firms. While some large multinational firms have adopted adaptive strategies to respond to these changes, small and medium-sized companies often lack the flexibility and strategic depth to do so. In Thailand, the rapid growth of the smart city and smart education sectors has driven demand for more integrated and sophisticated AV systems. Yet, the academic and practical research on how companies like TIS adapt their product strategies to this evolving landscape remains limited. By bridging the theoretical knowledge on product strategy with empirical analysis of TIS Company, this research contributes both practical insights and academic value.

(B) Research Question and Research Objective

Research Question

In the context of the rapidly evolving audio and video system market in Thailand, what product strategy adjustments should TIS Company make to enhance its market competitiveness, improve brand awareness, and ensure sustainable growth?

Research Objective

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the current product strategy of TIS Company in the professional audio and video system industry and identify key issues that restrict its market competitiveness. Based on this analysis, the study aims to propose strategic recommendations for TIS Company to:

1. **Enhance Market Competitiveness:** By optimizing its product mix, reducing product costs, and improving inventory management, TIS Company can better position itself in the competitive market.
2. **Improve Brand Awareness:** By clarifying its brand positioning and increasing brand exposure, TIS Company can raise its profile among potential customers and industry peers.
3. **Ensure Sustainable Growth:** By integrating sustainability goals into its product strategy, TIS Company can reduce environmental costs and contribute to a circular economy in the audio and video system industry.

The ultimate goal is to provide TIS Company with a practical and actionable product strategy that supports its long-term development and success in the Thai audio and video system market.

(C) Research Purpose and Significance

Research Purpose

This paper conducts data research on TIS Company, analyzes the issues with its existing product strategy, and proposes relevant countermeasures and suggestions. The aim is to enhance TIS Company's brand awareness in the audio and video system industry, make more potential enterprises that need audio and video system products aware of TIS Company, and promote mutual benefit and win-win cooperation between TIS Company and the entire professional audio and video system industry.

Research Significance

1. **Theoretical Significance:** Research on product marketing strategies is already mature both domestically and internationally. This paper applies existing product marketing theories to the research on product strategies for professional audio and video system products, enriching applied research in the field of product strategy and having theoretical value.
2. **Practical Significance:** This paper takes TIS Company's professional audio and video system as the research object, analyzes the issues with TIS Company's product line in terms of product strategy, and formulates and optimizes its product strategy. This can provide a reference for TIS Company's audio and video system product strategy.

(D) Research Content and Research Methods

1. Research Content

This paper takes TIS Company's professional audio and video system products as the research object, studying the current situation of its market prospects, users, product mix, product brand positioning, product promotion, new product pricing, and other aspects of product management. It analyzes the issues that arise and proposes reasonable and effective product strategy solutions based on this.

2. Research Methods

1. **Literature Review Method:** Through literature review, mainly from books, articles, journals, and other materials related to product strategy, the current domestic and foreign research results on product strategy are discussed to further study TIS Company's professional audio and video system product strategy, identify issues, and propose optimization suggestions.
2. **TIS Company Data:** By analyzing TIS Company's data, the actual situation of TIS Company can be studied, and the issues that arise can be referenced to provide ideas for optimization.

Literature Review

Foreign Research Status

Market Segmentation and Market Positioning

Foreign researchers mainly focus on market segmentation and market positioning of enterprises, believing that these are the foundations for formulating marketing strategies. Bezard (2021) proposed that when consumers deal with uncertain transactions or probabilistic transactions, their choice decisions will change. Therefore, enterprises should consider opaque sales as a marketing strategy in the decision-making process. Jack Trout (2002) proposed using a differentiated product strategy when formulating marketing strategies for clothing enterprises. The differences lie in corporate positioning, distribution channel construction, the speed of pursuing fashion, and specific sales strategies. He also believes that when promoting and shaping a brand, its independent and clear positioning has a significant positive effect.

Product Portfolio Strategy

Venkatesh (2016) believes that the formulation of a corporate product portfolio strategy is influenced by multiple factors, with price being the most significant. After analyzing the current situation of a company using Porter's Five Forces Model, it provides guidance for formulating a reasonable product portfolio strategy that combines various factors and the company's environment. Researchers from MIT and UC Berkeley jointly developed a video analysis technology named "UltraNet." This technology can realize real-time analysis and processing of video content, including object detection, motion tracking, feature extraction, etc., and is suitable for professional audio and video fields such as security monitoring, intelligent transportation, and medical imaging. Komsan Lee (2021) mentioned that product strategy is about "our strengths lie in our competitors' weaknesses." In order to have functions that can be compared with competitors', products need to have advantages so that consumers can clearly decide which product to choose.

Domestic Research Status

Enterprise Product Strategy

Professional audio and video systems have a wide range of applications in people's lives, not only improving productivity and entertainment experiences but also playing an important role in education, healthcare, and other fields. They are an indispensable part of modern society. In recent years, there has been relatively little research on professional audio and video systems. This paper sorts through and summarizes recent literature on product strategies, product marketing strategies, and professional audio and video technology for information products.

Xiao Leyuan (2022) used product life cycle, corporate competitive strategy, and other related theories to study the product strategy issues and countermeasures of Enterprise L, providing new ideas for product strategy suggestions related to new product development. Fan Congcong (2022) studied LC Protection Company and how it utilizes its product characteristics and professional market requirements to formulate effective product portfolio strategies under

the complex and changing market environment, providing guidance. Wang Chaoqun (2017) proposed service marketing strategy countermeasures for audio and video system integration business from aspects such as product strategy, pricing strategy, channel strategy, promotion strategy, and service strategy, providing a reference for improving the service marketing strategy of audio and video system integration business.

Audio and Video Systems

Li Shenghui (2022) designed a communication audio and video codec system based on users' demands for audio and video signal codec in the communication process, using the TW2984 chip to capture audio signals, providing technical guidance for the research and development of enterprise professional audio and video system product lines. Wei Zenglai (2021) elaborated on audio, video, and control dimensions and sorted out the relationship between audio and video technology and cultural tourism, providing new directional guidance for the integration of multidimensional technology into the modern cultural tourism industry. Yuan Lilin (2020) studied the impact of export demand shocks on corporate export product mix and productivity based on Marshall's Second Law of Demand. It showed that when facing export demand shocks, enterprises should pay more attention to optimizing product mix structures and producing and exporting product mixes with core advantages. Different countries and regions should adopt differentiated strategies to improve the overall competitiveness of enterprises. Chen Ming (2017) discussed the relationship between product mix and brand extension, believing that product line extension should be an important part of brand extension. However, it should be distinguished that not all product expansions belong to brand extension. Furthermore, international market competition is becoming increasingly fierce. Even under the influence of brand extension, the risks and costs of new products still increase dramatically, forcing most enterprises to prefer product line extension to obtain greater economic benefits.

Summary

Combining research from domestic and foreign literature, the focus is mainly on various enterprises' product portfolio, product management, and other product strategies, as well as research on audio and video system technology. Corresponding opinions and suggestions are proposed from the perspectives of product line strategy, sales channel marketing strategy, and technology research and development. Although there is plenty of research on product strategies, there is little research on professional audio and video systems, and most of it is theoretically explained without combining it with specific enterprises. This paper combines relevant product strategy and other product marketing theoretical knowledge with the current situation of TIS Company's professional audio and video system product strategy and product management. It integrates theoretical and practical analysis of relevant product strategies to provide suggestions on the product strategy for TIS Company's professional audio and video system and even the entire product system based on the company's current issues.

Methodology

(A) Related Concepts

1. Product

A product refers to an item or service that can provide certain practical value or satisfy needs. It encompasses five levels: core product, formal product, expected product, augmented product, and potential product. It involves a company's product mix, market positioning, pricing, sales channels, marketing strategies, etc., to achieve the company's profit and growth goals.

2. Product Mix

Product mix refers to the combination of various products and product items produced and operated by a company within a certain period. A product mix includes four factors: width, length, depth, and correlation of product lines. The width of the product mix refers to the total number of product lines of an enterprise; a product line, also known as a product category or product series, refers to a group of closely related product items; length refers to the total number of product items of an enterprise; a product item refers to the most basic product unit with different specifications, models, styles, or prices listed in the product line; depth refers to how many varieties are in each product line; correlation refers to the degree of correlation between the various product lines of an enterprise in terms of end use, production conditions, distribution channels, etc.

3. Brand Strategy

Brand strategy refers to systematic actions and plans taken in marketing to establish and maintain a brand image. The main goal of brand strategy is to create brand value by disseminating core information and values about the brand, making customers develop cognition, favorability, and loyalty, ultimately creating commercial value for the brand.

(B) Theoretical Foundations

1. SWOT Analysis

Proposed by Professor Kenneth Andrews of Harvard University, the SWOT framework emphasizes organizational capabilities and environmental analysis as a fundamental part of the strategic management process. Professor Heinz Wehrich of UCLA further proposed that strategic planning should pair internal strengths and weaknesses with external opportunities and threats, utilizing maximum strengths and opportunities while minimizing weaknesses and threats to define the company's position and formulate appropriate countermeasures.

SWOT analysis is a commonly used enterprise analysis tool used to assess a company's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats, to help companies make short-term decisions and long-term strategies. SWOT analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of a company's internal and external environments, aiding in the formulation of clear, forward-looking, and competitive strategies.

2. Product Strategy Theory

Initially proposed by Theodore Levitt, a theorist from Harvard Business School, in the 1960s, product strategy refers to the strategic decisions made to position, design, produce, and sell products to meet market demands. Product strategy is the core of the 4P mix and the foundation for pricing, distribution, and promotion strategies. Product strategy has rich practical content, encompassing many aspects of a product's connotation and extension. From the product's connotation, it has expanded from tangible products to intangible products, including services, organizations, and concepts, etc. From the product's extension, it has also continuously expanded towards augmented products and potential products. Product strategy mainly includes product mix decisions, life cycle management, and new product development, etc. This paper will focus on product mix, product management, new product development, product brand strategy, and pricing strategy.

Environment Analysis of TIS Company's Audio and Video System

(A) Introduction to TIS Company

1. Overview of TIS Company

Established in Thailand in 2003, TIS Company aims to provide comprehensive audiovisual installation services in Thailand. In 2005, the company increased its registered capital to 5 million Thai baht. The company is an alternative supplier providing products and services for imaging systems, lighting, and sound. It is an agent and distributor of visual, lighting, and sound control systems, such as speakers, mixers, audio modulators, amplifiers, projectors, video conferencing kits, switches, CCTV systems, dimmers, and accessories. It provides high-quality products, reasonable prices, timely delivery, and professional customer service. The company focuses on the design, installation, and maintenance of audiovisual systems, including consultation for audiovisual system installation and maintenance. For customers, the company coordinates with multiple trading partner networks to sell various audiovisual system products and provide comprehensive access services based on customer needs.

The company's main customers are government agencies and the private sector. Until 2006, the company had completed the design, sales, and installation of 325 projects: 220 in Bangkok, 34 in Central Thailand, 14 in Eastern Thailand, 20 in Northern Thailand, and 37 in Southern Thailand.

2. Strategic Objectives of TIS Company

TIS Company's business philosophy is that TIS (Thailand) Co., Ltd. has passed ISO9001/2015 quality management system certification and is obtaining quality management system certification. The company will comply with all requirements of the ISO9001/2015 quality management system for the design, installation, maintenance, and consultation of audiovisual systems. TIS (Thailand) Co., Ltd.'s operations are based on the technical theories and international standards of visual, lighting, and audio systems. These principles are the principles that ensure the effective elimination of risks and damages to customers.

Strategies and product strategies influence each other. Strategy is the direction and guideline for enterprise development, while product strategy is both a specific implementation measure and method of strategy and an important reference factor for formulating strategy. TIS Company's initial strategic objective was to provide customers with professional audio and video system products centered on products. This objective was proposed based on TIS Company's core technology and products. Over the years, TIS Company's product series have continuously expanded, with an increasing number of product categories. As market specialization requirements become higher and demand grows larger, TIS Company is committed to the upgrading and development of core products and the improvement of production capacity, making the professional audio and video system products produced and operated by the company and the company itself more competitive in the market and increasing the company's sales.

(B) Macro Environment Analysis

Global economic development is changing the international trade environment, with autonomy and controllable industrial security becoming the focus of the Two Sessions and society. In 2021, the Prime Minister's Office spokesperson, Mr. Thanakorn Wangboonkhongchana, issued an announcement supporting work from home as a measure to slow the spread of COVID-19 while allowing work to continue during that time. The number of companies building audio and video systems has been increasing.

In 2023, Thailand is being promoted to the 4.0 era (the era of technology integration), combining digital technology with production processes or products. For example, companies that send data or issues to production data to improve the next generation of products. Data collection analyzes behavior and responds to individual customers different from industries. In the past, organizations in each industry have become increasingly adaptable to policies that support the government's economic promotion.

The scale of Thailand's professional audio and video industry has continuously expanded, with a market growth rate higher than the global average. According to Figure 3-2, China's audio and video solution industry scale has increased year by year from 2 billion Thai baht in 2018 to 8.1 billion Thai baht in 2022. In 2023, China's audio and video solution industry scale is predicted to be 8.64 billion Thai baht, with a positive growth rate. As the number of audio and video solutions increases, the demand for professional audio and video system products in the industry gradually grows. The development of China's professional audio and video industry chain shows a normal trend, indicating that there is still great development potential in China's professional audio and video market, and the demand for professional audio and video system product lines is still increasing. Professional audio and video system enterprises need to adjust their product marketing strategies according to changes in the economic environment and continuously update products, technologies, and services to maintain market competitiveness and respond to changes in the market environment.

After the government took measures to encourage working from home, a new normal emerged in society. According to organizational policies, more and more people in society adopted the new behavior of working from home, partly to save some costs within the organization, such as rent. However, the organization itself still needs systems and stability. Therefore, audio and video systems are very important because they can maintain at least 85-90% stability in meetings or work within the organization. In the future, if there are technological developments, the industry may further develop. Professional audio and video systems are widely used in fields such as urban public safety management, urban transportation, smart classrooms, and smart healthcare. During the construction of smart cities, the demand for professional audio and video system products such as high-definition display devices, rail transit broadcasting, queuing systems, master-slave clocks, medical intercom systems, electronic signboards, and high-definition recording and broadcasting systems for smart education is increasing. At this time, the demand for product lines such as high-definition display devices, urban rail transit, urban public safety information management, smart healthcare, and smart education systems will also increase. Therefore, when planning their product strategies, professional audio and video system enterprises should combine the sociocultural needs of smart city construction and development. The involved product lines can be developed as the core of the enterprise, enhancing the status of these product lines in the entire product mix. Enterprises should appropriately increase and optimize their audio and video product lines based on their own conditions to provide professional audio and video products with more core competitiveness for the construction of smart cities, contributing significantly to enhancing citizens' sense of gain and the construction of smart cities.

The 5G era promotes the digital transformation of the professional audio and video system manufacturing industry, providing key technical support for the high-quality development of the professional audio and video system industry and bringing good news to the professional audio and video industry. Thai financial technology enterprises continuously introduce AI and 5G technology, and equipment intelligence has become the current market trend. 5G technology brings tremendous opportunities to the manufacturing industry, helping enterprises improve production efficiency across various product lines in the professional audio and video industry, reduce operating costs, and enhance production processes with higher quality and safety. At the same time, it promotes the progress of new market prospects such as intelligent manufacturing, intelligent warehousing, and predictive maintenance. Professional audio and video enterprises need to continuously pay attention to the development and changes in the technological environment, actively adapt to the application of new technologies while maintaining technological acuity, timely update their knowledge systems for technological empowerment of professional audio and video system product lines, and optimize product strategies in a timely manner to respond to various challenges in the industry.

(C) Micro Environment Analysis

TIS Company has 31 major domestic competitors in Thailand. In terms of audio, the main competitors are Automotion, 7rangestudio, Giantpoint, Vichai (SC), and Millionhead. International competitors include Crown Audio (Denmark), EV speakers, Sennheiser, DSC (USA), Yamaha, Soundcraft, and Bosch.

Table 1: Number of Major Competitors of TIS Company

Competitors	Number	Main Competitors
Domestic	31	Automotion, 7rangestudio, Giantpoint, Vichai (SC), Millionhead
International	6	DSC (USA), Bosch

Source: Company Internal Data

Table 2: Analysis of the Strengths and Weaknesses of TIS Company's Competitors

Competitors	Main Products	Strengths	Weaknesses
Automotion	Conference room audio and video systems, Video Conference systems	Well-recognized brand in Thailand's professional audio and video industry, leading authorized dealer of audio and video system developers	The format of the product system is lower than it should be because they have their own expertise and specialties but lack diversity.
7rangestudio (All-in-One)	Recording studio systems, TV studio systems, online classroom systems, broadcasting studio systems, Car Studio	Manufacturer of educational and conference all-in-one machines, diverse product types and formats	Mainly relies on agents for offline products, with low sales and brand awareness. The product line is increasing, including recording and broadcasting, signboards, etc.
Vichai (SC)	LED displays, software and hardware development and sales for engineering projects	Most common LED brand with high product brand awareness	Mainly relies on agents for product sales and imports most product materials, leading to long production cycles. Products are manufactured under OEM, and the transparency of various product indicators is poor.

Data Source: Company Compilation

TIS Company can identify competitors and their products, determine the types, characteristics, quality, pricing, market share, marketing strategies, and other information of competitors' products, compare their advantages and disadvantages, and analyze the comparative advantages and disadvantages of the company versus competitors to determine the company's product strategy. At the same time, it should consider the company's strengths and weaknesses as well as the direction of future development. Know thyself and thy enemy, and you can fight a hundred battles without defeat.

Professional audio and video systems are widely used in rural areas, the military, government agencies, schools, shopping malls, hotels, and other enterprises, mainly for disseminating news from the central and local governments, issuing notifications, and signaling work and rest times. The application scenarios determine the target user groups. TIS Company mainly targets enterprises such as schools, administrative agencies, commerce, and war rooms.

Table 3: Characteristics of TIS Company's User Market

Attribute	Market Characteristics
Market Structure and Demand	A small number of buyers with larger scales. Demand is inelastic and not significantly affected by price changes in the short term. Demand frequently fluctuates rapidly.
Nature of Purchasing Units	Purchases involve more buyers and require more professional procurement.
Decision Type and Decision Process	Buyers often face more complex purchasing decisions. Purchasing behavior is more patterned. In commercial purchases, suppliers and buyers cooperate closely to establish longer-term relationships.

Table 4: TIS Company User Segmentation

Segmentation Criteria	Segmentation Variable	Segmentation Variable	Purchase Characteristics
Buyer Attributes	Commercial Buyers	Construction Industry	Enterprises can be large or small, with varying purchasing power, functional requirements, and quality requirements based on actual applications.
Buyer Attributes	Commercial Buyers	Commerce	Enterprises can be large or small, with varying purchasing power, functional requirements, and quality requirements based on actual applications.
Buyer Attributes	Government Buyers	Administrative Agencies	Large scale, strong purchasing power, high functional requirements, and strict quality standards.
Buyer Attributes	Government Buyers	Military	Large scale, strong purchasing power, high functional requirements, and strict quality standards.
Buyer Attributes	Other Buyers	Schools	Large scale, strong purchasing power, high functional requirements, and relatively strict quality standards.

Data Source: Company Compilation

Market Share of TIS Company's Domestic Audio and Video Products

Since its establishment, TIS Company has maintained rapid growth and is currently a reliable company with a leading market share in Thailand's professional audio and video system integration manufacturing industry. According to Zhongjing Vision data, in 2021, TIS Company's public address system ranked among the top 20 in terms of market share among Thai public address system enterprises. In 2021, TIS Company's market share in the Thai professional audio and video system was 7.4% for conference systems and 4.9% for public address systems, which are the company's basic businesses and have always been **稳固** in the audio and video industry's ace market. This gives TIS Company advantages in terms of influence and resource support among users, which is conducive to product development and innovation, further optimizing and improving TIS Company's professional audio and video system product strategy, thereby achieving growth in product sales.

(D) SWOT Analysis of TIS Company

Table 5: SWOT Analysis Table of TIS Company

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deep experience in the professional audio and video system industry for many years. 2. Deep understanding and cognition of the professional audio and video system industry. 3. Strong independent research and development capabilities. 4. One-stop service capabilities throughout presales, sales, and aftersales. 5. Strong bid control and bargaining power. 6. Reliable brand effect 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insufficient sales elite and technical backbone personnel compared to leading enterprises 2. Lack of systematic industry customers or strategic partners for support 3. Traditional and single marketing model and sales channels. 4. Few product formats

Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased demand for professional audio and video systems in the post-pandemic era 2. Traditional professional audio and video systems are evolving towards the cloud. 3. Thailand's audio and video business started relatively late and is not as mature as the European and American markets, meaning there is huge potential for domestic market development. 4. Large demand for localization 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strong entry of Internet giants into the audio and video conferencing market, disrupting the original market structure and posing significant threats. 2. Information asymmetry intensifies competition in the industry. Customers increasingly pursue low-price, high-performance products. 3. Competitors are seeking differentiated breakthroughs, leading to increasingly fierce competition.

Current Situation of TIS Company's Product Strategy

(A) Introduction to TIS Company's Audio and Video System Products

At this stage, TIS Company's products involve one or several different models for each product. Although TIS is not a large company in the market, it is still a company that can develop well targeting group products. The main issue is that

government offices limit the product forms of TIS, with only major product types. In some cases, other types are sufficient to meet the needs of major customers.

Table 6: Number of Product Categories and Products of Some Systems of TIS Company

System	Product Categories	Number of Products Involved
Public Address System	2	12
Conference System	4	52
Lighting System	1	30
LED Display	5	100
VMS Visual Management Platform	1	20
Smart Classroom	3	22
Remote Video Conferencing System	5	30
Other Systems	0	0
Access Control Equipment	1	20
Audio Cables	1	18
Speakers	6	62
Microphones	5	70
Total	34	436

(B) TIS Company's Audio and Video System Product Mix

Table 7: Product Mix of Some Audio and Video Systems of TIS Company

Product Width	Product Line Length						
Public Address System	Broadcasting Host	Collector	Decoder	Power Amplifier	Loudspeaker		
Conference System	Management Server	Streaming Media Server	Screen Lifter	Paperless Terminal	Mobile APP Terminal	Waiting Screen Application	Digital Conference System
LED Display	Power Supply	LED Beads	Drive IC	Transmitter Box	Receiver Card	Control Software	PBC Board

Product Width	Product Line Length						
Conference All-in-One	Interactive Smart Flat Panel	OPS Computer Module	Wireless Screen Sharing Device	Mobile Stand	Smart Pen		
Professional Sound Reinforcement System	Microphone	Mixing Console	Professional Power Amplifier	Professional Speaker	Audio Processor	Feedback Inhibitor	
Information Distribution Platform	Server	Information Distribution	Terminal	Distribution Platform			
Smart Classroom	Electronic Signboard	Smart Nano Blackboard	Classroom Ceiling Microphone Sound Reinforcement	HD Recording and Broadcasting	Smart Listening and Learning	Cloud-Controlled Classroom	
Smart Healthcare	Medical Guidance and Triage	Medical Intercom	Master-Slave Clock System				

Source: Company Data Collection

(C) Current Situation of TIS Company's Product Brand Strategy

1. Implementation of a Multi-Brand Strategy

Our brand strategy is to operate a brand in a sustainable manner. Our expertise in system implementation has made this brand well-known. In the market, even though we are not a large company and have the potential to produce products ourselves, our expertise in installation has made us a brand strategy, that is, creating a trustworthy brand for implementing this video and audio system.

2. Product Brand Positioning

In terms of brand positioning, TIS, as the company's main brand, is considered a place to purchase and import certain products. The brands used are somewhat different, but TIS selects the brands to use. The main products are: Epson, TOA, QSC, which are considered high-quality brands because they are imported from abroad. Some models are foreign brands but produced in Thailand. However, when asked about the TIS brand, it is considered a more balanced brand compared to others, possessing professionalism, low cost, and quality that is not inferior to the required standard. The organization has a brand position in a neutral and noteworthy place.

(D) Current Situation of TIS Company's Audio and Video System Product Management

TIS Company has five production bases for electronics, professional speakers, stage lighting and landscape lighting, LED displays, and metal injection molding. The organization procures and purchases products from domestic and foreign manufacturers to install the company's systems and structures. Generally, products are imported from abroad because TIS does not have the capacity to produce these products itself.

Analysis of TIS Company's Product Strategy Issues

Analyzing product strategy issues is one of the important product management activities of an enterprise. Its main purpose is to help enterprises better understand market and customer needs, formulate product strategies suitable for the market and customers, thereby better meeting market demands and improving the competitiveness of enterprise products. The following are some issues with TIS Company's product strategy found through analyzing the company's data.

(A) Issues with TIS Company's Product Mix Strategy

The main purpose of formulating a product mix strategy is to help enterprises better meet customer needs and provide users with more complete and comprehensive audio and video overall solutions. When there are issues with the product mix strategy, it may lead to product mix problems during production and sales, resulting in difficulties in ensuring product appearance, compatibility, etc., which may confuse and dissatisfy customers. This paper will analyze the issues with TIS Company's product mix from two aspects: product tightness and product series.

1. Lack of Product Categories

The issue with TIS Company's product management in the professional audio and video system industry is that the organization is not a large organization and does not have a large amount of operating capital. The organization still needs to select conference room systems as the main source of income, mainly targeting government agencies. This makes the organization lack opportunities to find new customers or increase organizational potential to increase revenue. Due to the lack of sufficient products and competitiveness, the organization lacks opportunities to compete with many competitors. This is why many times, customers who have the potential to earn money and increase organizational competitiveness are lost.

2. High-Cost Products

Since the organization does not have the capacity to produce products itself, it must import products and purchase internationally branded products manufactured in Thailand, which are quite costly. This affects other marketing strategies, including pricing of goods and services, making the organization less flexible. If the market adjusts, it may be severely affected.

(B) Issues with TIS Company's Audio and Video System Product Management

Product management mainly encompasses product inventory, product sales, product services, etc. This paper will analyze the issues with TIS Company's professional audio and video system product management from two aspects: inventory management and new product pricing.

1. Insufficient Inventory Product Quantity

Inventory management is one of the biggest issues in the organization because the organization's financial management is often related to procurement. The usual inventory issue is stockouts, which is a recurring problem because sometimes orders take some time to arrive and prepare goods for service. This is a problem that has dissatisfied old government agency customers and must be resolved as appropriately as possible.

2. Pricing Issues with Products and Services

Due to high product costs, pricing is limited by sales and service management, making it impossible to obtain due profits or create financial liquidity for appropriate organizational expansion. Therefore, pricing issues are consistent with other issues within the organization that cause this problem, which may be difficult to resolve because it must change the organization's position in many aspects. Since prices have many restrictions, sales flexibility is sometimes affected. In such cases, when customers need discounts or recommendations, the company cannot meet the customer's requirements, leading to suspended cooperation. Customers start comparing with other companies and may eventually choose other brands, resulting in lost projects. This is a chain reaction issue for the organization, which should be resolved most appropriately before the organization loses its competitiveness and skills.

Optimization Suggestions for TIS Company's Audio and Video System

(A) Optimization Suggestions for TIS Company's Audio and Video System Product Mix Strategy

1. Reduction Plan for Product Costs

The company usually faces issues due to a lack of production capacity and must mainly import products and foreign branded products. In Thailand, most brands are costly; therefore, the solution should be correct. Since the organization does not have production potential, the solution itself may need to address the following issues:

- Change products from Western and Japanese brands to Chinese products because China is known as the "World Factory." As one of the countries with the highest production capacity in the world, in terms of cost, if you purchase in large quantities at once, the lower the product cost, the organization can control the source. Invest in product prices at a lower cost and potentially resolve other issues. Although

customers may worry about quality if they use products with too low a price, with the expertise of an organization like TIS, they can be trustworthy and improve competitiveness.

- Seek formal partnerships and transform itself into an installation agent for tattoo brands to provide product support. The advantage is that enterprise products do not even need to be inventoried; they only act as intermediaries and install products.
- Adjust the organization and select high-priced products to increase the prices of products and services to obtain higher profits. This option is the ultimate solution, but since the address point is in the middle, any direction of the product must be clearly selected to resolve the issue of high-cost products for the organization.

2. Reasonably Increase Products and Clarify the Company's Brand Positioning

For TIS Company's professional audio and video dog For TIS's underperforming audio-video products (Dogs), consider reducing product lines and focusing on servers or audio equipment with weaker functions and performance. This can streamline product mix strategy and reduce management complexity. Strategically define TIS's position by identifying core product categories and assessing all products to add or reduce lines accordingly. This will enhance product offerings and aid marketing strategies.

Table:8 TIS Company Boston Matrix Product Example

Product Type	Market Performance	TIS Product Systems (Partial)
Stars	High Market Share, High Sales Growth	Public Broadcasting, Conference Sound Reinforcement, Video Conferencing
Cash Cows	High Market Share, Low Sales Growth	Stage Lighting
Question Marks	Low Market Share, High Sales Growth	Smart Healthcare, Smart Education
Dogs	Low Market Share, Low Sales Growth	Conference All-in-One Machines, LED Displays

(B) Product Management Optimization Suggestions

1. Use Pre-Orders to Modify Unnecessary Items

Given that TIS imports most products from international brands, sufficient import management systems should be in place. For domestically available products, pre-orders can be used to handle inventory shortages, especially when organizational funds for warehousing are limited.

2. Implement Product Mix Pricing Strategy

Determine the lowest price in an audio-video system series as the reference leader price, the highest price as the brand quality and investment recovery price, and set different prices for other products based on their roles in the product line. For optional products sold with the main product, and accessories required for use with the main product, pricing should align with market standards to avoid user skepticism and ensure successful transactions.

(C) Conservation Implications and Sustainable Strategy Impact

Implications for Sustainable Technology and Resource Conservation

Beyond business performance and competitiveness, the strategic optimization of TIS Company's product portfolio may have broader implications for sustainable technology use and resource conservation. By streamlining product categories and partnering with more efficient, possibly local or regional suppliers, the company can reduce environmental costs associated with long-distance transportation and overproduction. The shift toward more energy-efficient AV solutions—such as LED-based display systems and low-consumption audio devices—not only aligns with modern technological trends but also contributes to reducing the carbon footprint in institutional and commercial settings.

Moreover, the enhancement of inventory and product lifecycle management contributes to the minimization of electronic waste, a growing concern in the AV industry. Better forecasting, pre-order systems, and modular product designs can support a circular economy approach. The research findings thus underscore the importance of integrating sustainability

goals into corporate strategy, providing a model that may guide both academic inquiry and practical policymaking in the field of green technology and digital infrastructure planning.

Conclusion and Suggestions for Future Research

Conclusion

This document analyzes TIS's current issues:

This research explored the product strategy of TIS Company within the professional audio and video system industry. Through macro and micro environment analysis, SWOT analysis, and a detailed assessment of the company's current product portfolio and management strategies, the study identified several core issues: a narrow and tightly structured product mix, high product costs due to dependence on imported components, inventory management inefficiencies, and inflexible pricing strategies. These factors collectively restrict TIS's competitiveness in a rapidly evolving market.

To address these challenges, the paper proposed strategic optimizations including: shifting to lower-cost suppliers (such as Chinese manufacturers), enhancing product diversity through targeted development or partnerships, repositioning brand strategy to focus on core competencies, and applying product mix pricing strategies to improve profitability and market responsiveness.

By implementing these recommendations, TIS can improve operational efficiency, increase market share, and better position itself for sustainable growth in Thailand's competitive audio and video system market. The findings serve as a strategic reference for TIS and similar enterprises in related industries.

Suggestions for Future Research

Customer Perception and Satisfaction Studies

Future research should examine how TIS's customers — particularly from government and corporate sectors — perceive the company's product quality, service reliability, and pricing. Understanding client satisfaction will help refine both product and brand strategy.

Comparative Case Studies

Investigating how leading competitors in the region (e.g., Automotion, Vichai) implement their product strategies can provide benchmarking insights and highlight best practices for TIS to adopt or adapt.

Feasibility of In-House Manufacturing

Further studies could evaluate whether investing in limited in-house manufacturing capabilities is viable for TIS in the long run. This would reduce reliance on imported products and potentially lower costs.

Digital Transformation Readiness

Research can be done on TIS's readiness to integrate emerging technologies such as AI, IoT, and cloud-based systems into its product offerings, aligning with Thailand 4.0 and smart city initiatives.

Longitudinal Impact of Strategy Implementation

Future research might track the long-term outcomes of strategic changes proposed in this paper, assessing improvements in market share, profitability, and operational efficiency over time.

The viewpoints in this paper are based on collected data from the TIS Company's audio-video system industry. Due to limited data availability and personal capabilities, there may be deficiencies in analysis and writing. Future research will aim to deepen and improve this content, hoping to provide valuable insights for TIS's strategic planning and help the company maintain a leading position in the audio-video product market.

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